

Introduction

Following the introduction of the different vaccines against CoViD-19 there appeared to be serious adverse effects being reported. This caused a great deal of speculation on different social media platforms, particularly those opposed to these vaccines. The main focus of these concerns and speculations appeared to be the development of myocarditis within a few days of the person receiving the vaccine. This appears to be mainly attributed to the spike protein that is produced in response to the vaccines, specifically Moderna/BioNTech's mRNA1273 and Pfizer's BNT1262b both of which use mRNA.

Although the spike protein appears to be an obvious reason for these cases, other possible reasons should not be dismissed, therefore in an effort to understand these concerns and whether there could be alternative explanations, multiple published papers have been accessed and examined. This has resulted in an evolving, hopefully coherent, alternative hypothesis to the spike protein hypothesis.

Introduction

This paper examines data surrounding adverse events that have been reported as being associated with the different vaccines against CoViD-19, presented in part 1.

Following on from the analysis of the published data is the development of a hypothesis as to a feasible cause for the observed adverse events and is presented in Part 2.

Part 1 Published Data

Literature Search

Myocarditis appears to be the adverse effect of the different CoViD-19 vaccines that is causing the most consternation a search of the published literature using the term “myocarditis after Covid19 vaccination” in Google Scholar, PubMed and Science Direct was made. Editorial results were not included in the review but correspondence reporting cases were included alongside full papers, with particular emphasis on articles that were open access. Further searches were completed based on information contained in the returned results, irrespective of the system affected and any new reported adverse effects, articles used in this discussion are summarised in Table 11 of the supplementary data.

Finally, further literature searches were undertaken to obtain papers published prior to the CoViD-19 vaccine to determine whether similar events have occurred with other vaccines or medications in the past.

Data Synthesis and Analysis

In all 47 papers were retrieved that described 168 possible adverse events related to four vaccines Janssen Ad26COVS1 (2/168), AstraZeneca ChAdOx1 (16/168), Moderna/BioNTech's mRNA1273 (62/168) and Pfizer's BNT1262b (86/168).

Of the 168 adverse events reported the following were excluded from the initial analysis:

An elderly patient suffered a myocardial infarction one hour after receiving the mRNA1273 vaccine that was considered coincidental (Boivin & Martin 2021).

Three deaths that followed BNT1262b vaccination were deemed to be unrelated to the vaccine (Edler et al 2021).

Two patients had a vaccine administered where neither the vaccine or the dosage is provided. (e Silva et al 2022).

Three were diagnosed as having Drug Induced Hypersensitivity Syndrome (DIHS) relating to medication commenced before the vaccination, one following mRNA1273 and two following BNT1262b. (Korekwa et al 2022).

Fourteen deaths temporally associated with vaccination were found to have no evidence of a causal association following autopsy, 4 followed the BNT162b2 vaccine, 8 followed ChAdOx1 and 2 followed mRNA1273. (Schneider et al 2021).

Two had myocardial infarctions within 24 hours of receiving the mRNA1273 vaccine, both of whom had personal or family history of coronary artery disease which were considered unrelated to the vaccine. (Sung et al 2021).

Thus there are 143 adverse events that appear to be linked with the vaccines, with 2 being associated with Ad26COVS1, 8 being associated with ChAdOx1, 56 being associated with mRNA1273 and 77 being associated with BNT1262b.

Of the 143 adverse events 27 followed after the first vaccination, 91 followed the second vaccination and 23 followed the third vaccination, with 2 having no dose

information given, both Ad26COVS1, therefore this vaccine has been disregarded in the initial analysis. The number of adverse events associated with each vaccine and the dose after which they occurred (Supplementary data tables 1a, 1b, 1c).

In an attempt to quantify these differences further the adverse events are further dissembled on the basis of sex and vaccine (Supplementary data tables 1 to 3). It should be noted that the data for the third dose of mRNA1273 were obtained from a number of healthcare workers who were all tested for raised troponin levels on day three after the third dose, the majority of whom were female (Buergin et al 2023), which may be a source of bias.

Number of adverse events following 1st dose by vaccine and sex

Number of adverse events following 2nd dose by vaccine and sex

Number of adverse events following 3rd dose by vaccine and sex

Of the 141 cases for which there is dose information, 18 (14.2%) had diagnoses other than myocarditis, of which 7/18 followed ChAdOx1 vaccination and 10/18 followed BNT1262b vaccination. Additionally, the two cases which had no vaccine data also had diagnoses other than myocarditis (e Silva et al 2022).

Myocarditis was diagnosed in 123 cases with 1/123 (0.8%) following ChAdOx1, 56/123 (45.5%) following mRNA1273 and 66/123 (53.7%) following BNT1262b. In addition one case of myocarditis was reported following Ad26COVS1 which had no dose information (Rosner et al 2021).

A total of 14 deaths were reported as being associated with the vaccines all following autopsy.

3/14 had identified causes other than myocarditis and included the development of anti-PF4 antibodies causing abnormal clotting. Two were considered highly likely and followed a single dose of ChAdOx1 with the third considered possible following a single dose of Ad26COVS1 (Schneider et al 2021).

11/14 deaths were attributed to myocarditis, all of which followed the mRNA based vaccines. 8/11 followed the BNT1262b vaccine, of which 4 occurred after the first dose and 4 occurred after the second dose. (Ameratunga et al 2022; Minato et al 2024; Cho et al 2023; Schneider et al 2021). The remaining 3 deaths followed the mRNA1273 vaccine, 1 occurring after the first dose and 2 occurring after the second dose (Cho et al 2023)

Age Profiles by sex and adverse event

Although the information relating to the vaccine administered and the number of doses administered is a useful starting point, analysis based on sex/age and the time between the vaccination and the onset of the adverse event will provide further useful information that may be suggestive of the mechanism involved.

The initial step is to stratify all of the reported adverse events by age, this was achieved by dividing the participants into one of eight decades, with the total number of adverse events in each decade being determined (Table 2a). However, the participants from Montgomery et al (2022) had age information as a range of 20-51 years with a median 25. Similarly Gill et al (2022b) refers to the male participant as being “middle aged” which has no specific numerical definition, These have been included as being an undefined age group. Although data from Dionne et al (2021) also refers to an age range, these have been incorporated as all of the subjects fall into a single age band (11-20) (supplementary data Table 2a)

Adverse events by age group

All adverse events were further divided into myocarditis and other non myocarditis, again using the eight age ranges, with the additional step of separating each age group based on sex (Supplementary data Table 3a). As in the discussion above the data from Montgomery et al (2022) and Gill et al (2022b) have been included as an undefined age group.

It is notable that for myocarditis the ratio of males to females in the 11 to 20 and 21 to 30 is significant, in the older age groups the ratio reduces significantly, ultimately reversing in the 61-70 age group, although other conditions start to appear.

Finally, the adverse events that resulted in death were stratified according to age and whether the deaths were associated with myocarditis or other causes (Supplementary data Table 3b).

The data as analysed provides some insight into the issue of adverse events, but is inadequate to draw any meaningful conclusions as to possible causes or mechanism.

Further insight may be obtained by examining the time between vaccination and the onset of the adverse event. The first phase is to determine after which dose, which vaccine and whether the period between the dose and the adverse effect is 7 days or less or more than 7 days, (supplementary data tables 1a,1b, 1c).

From the above graphs it appears that most adverse events occur within 7 days of the specified dose, therefore it is worth examining the time between any dose and an adverse event. However, this analysis cannot include all of the pertinent studies due to the methods of reporting the information.

Amiodo et al (2023) report on two individuals who developed myocarditis after the vaccination and had a relapse several months later, although their initial response has been included this could be a source of inaccuracy; Ibrahim et al (2022) fails to report on the elapsed time between vaccination and symptoms appearing; Montgomery et al (2022), not only gives an age range but also a range of time between vaccination and onset (0.5 to 4 days) and mean of 50 hours (2.08 days). Although age related data from Dionne et al (2021) was incorporated in the age banding above, this study has to be excluded from any detailed consideration of time to onset as only a range of 1 to 6 days with a median of three days is provided.

For the remaining reports the following frequency table has been created:

Time between vaccination and adverse event (Days)	Number of events
0.2	1
0.25	3
1	10
1.5	1
2	12
2.5	1
3	47
4	5
5	3
6	2
7	3
10	2
12	1
14	4
16	1
49	2
84	1

From this data it appears that 3 days post vaccination may be significant, irrespective of which dose provoked the adverse event. Although not included but it may be important that the data from Dionne et al (2021) gives a median of 3 days and the data from Montgomery et al (2021) provides an average of just over 2 days. However, it is difficult to draw any specific conclusions.

Part 2 Hypersensitivity hypothesis development

It is proposed that a potential cause of the majority of the cases in this study is hypersensitivity to one or more components of the vaccines. To support the hypothesis an historical perspective has been incorporated.

Historical Perspective

Myocarditis following medication is not a new phenomenon, with Löffler (1936) describing the condition and the involvement of eosinophils; French & Weller (1942) reported on myocarditis following sulphonamide medication; Pfister and Plice (1950) report of a patient who had a prolonged reaction to penicillin that was accompanied by myocardial infarction however the authors did not attribute that event with the penicillin; Gardiol et al (1957) identified myocarditis following the administration of Tuberculostatic medication, with Al Ali et al (2006) listing other medications that can cause hypersensitivity myocarditis.

Similarly, myocarditis following vaccinations against Diphtheria, tetanus and pertussis vaccination (Amsel et al 1986); Diphtheria, Tetanus and Polio vaccination (Boccaro et al 2001); single tetanus vaccination (Dilber et al 2003, Yamamoto et al 2018); influenza (Engler et al 2015) and smallpox (Cassimatis et al 2003; Murphy et al 2003; Eckart et al 2004; Engler et al 2015; Keinath et al 2018).

Furthermore myocarditis has also been reported following black widow spider bite (Emara et al 2023; Kara et al 2013; Yaman et al 2015); Brown recluse spider bite (Sims et al 2021); tick bite (Okutsu et al 2022); viper snake bite (Kumar et al 2017).

Further, coronary artery spasm has been postulated as a contributory factor in some forms of ischaemic heart disease (Luchi et al 1979) and such a spasm triggered by histamine, as released during an allergic reaction, could manifest as angina, giving rise to the term allergic angina (Kounis & Zavras 1991). Although increased histamine in patients with Prinzmetal angina has been reported, no mechanism has been suggested (Sakata et al 1996). An extension to the theory is that in the majority of cases of unstable angina or

myocardial infarction there may be a combination of coronary artery spasm with atheromatous plaque erosion followed by the formation of thrombi, based on the fact that histamine is a powerful vasodilator which is released when mast cells degranulate alongside tryptase and chymase, which can denature collagen leading to plaque erosion or rupture leading to acute coronary syndrome (Kounis et al 1999). A later paper describing a case of angina and one case of myocardial infarction as the result of allergic reactions to shellfish coined the phrase “Kounis Syndrome” in describing these events (Zavras et al 2003). Kounis syndrome is defined as acute coronary syndrome accompanied by evidence of mast cell activation including hypersensitivity, it is similar to hypersensitivity myocarditis, but the main difference is that the latter presents with eosinophils, atypical lymphocytes and giant cells being present in heart tissue. Triggers for Kounis Syndrome appears to include drugs such as anticoagulants and non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; conditions such as food allergy and bronchial asthma; exposure to bites and stings (Kounis et al 2011, Kounis et al 2012, Kounis et al 2015, Kounis et al 2018a).

As the presence of eosinophils and other cells in myocardial tissue distinguishes hypersensitivity myocarditis from Kounis Syndrome, a review of of the different types of hypersensitivity and their aetiology is discussed.

Hypersensitivity Classification

A hypersensitivity reaction is an adverse event that results from an exaggerated inflammatory or immune response to an antigen/allergen.

There are four types of hypersensitivity that were first described by Gell and Coombs(1963):

Type	Name	Examples	Mediators
I	Allergy (immediate)	Anaphylaxis Asthma Allergic rhinitis Angioedema Food allergy	IgE
II	Antibody dependent cytotoxic	Autoimmune anaemias, thrombocytopenias	IgG, IgM
III	Immune complex disease	Systemic lupus erythematosus Reactive arthritis	(IgG, IgM, antigen) complexes, complement
IV	Delayed-type hypersensitivity, cell-mediated, antibody- independent	Contact dermatitis Tuberculosis Chronic transplant rejection	T cells, monocytes macrophages,

Hypersensitivity types (Marshall et al 2018)

However, further subtypes have been incorporated into the basic structure:

(Uzzaman and Cho 2012, Dispenza 2019):

Type	Sensitisation required	Mediators/reactants	Presentation examples	Typical time to onset
I	Yes	Mast cell mediated, IgE dependent	Anaphylaxis; urticaria; angioedema; asthma; allergic rhinitis	Minutes to 24 hours (Barker 2022b)
IIa	Yes	Antibody-mediated cytotoxic reactions (IgG and IgM antibodies complement often involved)	Immune cytopaenias	Within 24 hours (Justiz Vaillant et al 2023)
IIb	Yes	Antibody-mediated cell-stimulating reactions	Graves disease and chronic idiopathic urticaria	
III	Yes	Immune complex-mediated reactions complement involved	Serum sickness and vasculitis	
IVa	Yes	Th1 cell-mediated reactions macrophage activation	Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus contact dermatitis	72-96 hours (Barker 2022c)
IVb	Yes	Th2 cell-mediated reactions eosinophilic inflammation	Persistent asthma Persistent allergic rhinitis	
IVc	Yes	Cytotoxic T cell-mediated (perforin/granzyme B involved)	Stevens-Johnson syndrome	
IVd	Yes	T-cell-mediated neutrophilic inflammation	Behcet disease	
	No	pseudoanaphylaxis, IgE independent (previously anaphylactoid)	Similar to Type I	Minutes to 24 hours

To advance the alternative hypothesis the adverse events introduced and discussed earlier will be reconsidered in conjunction within the framework of the different types of hypersensitivity reaction. By examining after which dose the event occurred, the time to onset and any abnormal cells identified as being present with the aim is to classify adverse events as possible hypersensitivity types.

Although there are 26 cases that report the adverse events occurred after the first dose it is difficult to attribute this to the only hypersensitivity type that does not require previous exposure, particularly in those who have a delayed reaction.

An alternative that has been suggested is that the myocarditis may be an autoimmune response triggered by molecular mimicry in some people, particularly if it occurs after the first dose (Bozkurt et al 2021, Larson et al 2021, Alizadeh 2022).

Bozkurt et al (2021) further state that D'Angelo et al (2021) ruled out a delayed hypersensitivity reaction, when it was actively considered by them. It is further asserted that nanolipids and other excipients have not been shown to produce an immune response. Calogiuri et al (2019) argue that both polyethylene glycols and polysorbates can cause IgE reactions, echoing Stone et al (2019) who suggest that hypersensitivity to a Polyethylene Glycol may be directly proportional to its molecular weight.

Polyethylene Glycol (PEG) has been associated with complement activation-related pseudo allergy (CARPA), (Mohamed et al 2019, Inglut et al 2020 & Klimek et al 2021), with Antolin-Amerigo et al(2015) reporting on a case of PEG allergy in a painter.

Similarly, Polysorbate 80, in the Human papillomavirus vaccine, has been associated with hypersensitivity reactions although not myocarditis (Badiu et al 2012, Coors et al 2005, Liew et al 2008).

According to Kounis et al (2021) PEG and other vaccine related excipients are found in a wide variety of creams, lotions, cosmetic products, and some dental materials which could sensitise users of these products, estimating that up to 5.4% of the population are so sensitised, therefore both PEG and polysorbate 80 should be considered as possible causes of hypersensitivity (Ikediobi et al 2022). It has to be considered that the individuals who experienced adverse events following a single dose had previous exposure to a particular allergen that acted as the sensitising mechanism for any allergen in the vaccine.

The second factor to consider is based on typical time to onset. As shown above most symptoms appear between 3 and 4 days post exposure, which may suggest a Type IV hypersensitive reaction, although this time to onset is not definitive. Less than two days between second vaccination and onset could indicate a Type I reaction, as the first

vaccination provided the pre-sensitisation, however this is considered unlikely with the evidence at hand.

The third factor to consider is the involvement of eosinophils, which is suggestive of a Type IVb reaction, unfortunately the number of cases where eosinophils were definitely looked for is very limited, particularly those with myocarditis. What cannot be stated categorically is that the other cases of myocarditis with a similar time to onset of symptoms are devoid of eosinophilic involvement. The lack of peripheral eosinophilia cannot be assumed to rule out the involvement of eosinophils as the only definitive way of determining eosinophil involvement that is independent of the presence of eosinophilia is myocardial biopsy (Akl et al 2016, Sohn et al 2006, Montgomery et al 2021).

However, it is suggested that clinical presentation, rapid recovery and lack of evidence for alternative causes is consistent with hypersensitivity myocarditis, despite the lack of confirmatory myocardial biopsy (Montgomery et al 2021), therefore these are considered to be possible eosinophilic hypersensitivity reactions. Additionally, 15 cases of myocarditis in 12-18 year olds (Dionne et al 2021) and 7 cases in 14-19 year olds (Marshall et al 2021) having similar clinical trajectories that may suggest that they too should be included as possible eosinophilic hypersensitivity myocarditis cases.

Mouch et al (2021) report that each their cases were negative for eosinophilia but tested positive for IgG antibodies for both Epstein Barr Virus and Cytomegalovirus, Human Herpes Virus 4 and 5 (HHV-4 & HHV-5) respectively. Amodio et al (2023) report on both of their cases having reoccurrence of myocarditis several months after their first episodes, with both testing positive for HHV-7. Jaworski et al (2021) report on an 8 year old with myocarditis that appears to be secondary to HHV-6 and HHV-7 infection, with Ozdemir et al (2017) reporting myocarditis in 4/8 paediatric cases having positive assays for HHV-7. Of relevance is that the reactivation of various herpes viruses appears to be linked to a shift from Th1 mediated immune response to Th2 mediated immune response with

increased Th2 cytokines.(Mehta et al 2013). The type IVb hypersensitive response is also Th2 cell mediated, therefore whether the identified activation of HHV-4, HHV-5, HHV-6 and HHV-7 is the result of a hypersensitivity reaction needs to be considered.

As noted earlier there is a disproportionate ratio of males to females in the youngest age groups and consideration should be given as to whether this reflects responses to potential allergens that are related to the sex of the individual. It is established that oestrogen facilitates a Th2 response by modulating the production of Th1 inflammatory cytokines whilst stimulating the production of Th2 cytokines (Salem 2004). Furthermore oestrogen appears to be implicated in the degranulation of eosinophils, but limits their systemic spread (Townsend et al 2012). Conversely, testosterone appears to facilitate the production of Th1 cytokines thus Th1 response in males (Giron-Gonzalez et al 2000). This raises the question as to whether these differences in sex hormones is responsible for the wide difference between the rate of myocarditis between the sexes.

Discussion and Further Work

The current hypothesis, that myocarditis is precipitated by the spike protein created as a result of the vaccines, may have developed following the discovery of higher levels of spike protein not attached by antibodies in people with myocarditis compared with those without myocarditis (Yonker et al 2023). Other vaccines, most notably those against smallpox and influenza also induce myocarditis therefore it is postulated that the raised levels of circulating unattached spike protein may not be the cause of the myocarditis but are, instead, an indicator of immune system dysregulation (Yonker et al 2023).

An alternative hypothesis has been proposed whereby myocarditis and other CoViD-19 vaccine related adverse events maybe due to hypersensitivity to one or more of the excipients in the vaccines, with eosinophil infiltration into cardiac tissue being the precipitating cause.

DeMello et al (1990) indicate that patients who die from Drug Induced Hypersensitivity are rarely very ill prior to death, with arrhythmia being the cause of death rather than myocardial failure. Also, that as the disease progresses peripheral eosinophilia reduces to zero as eosinophils migrate into the tissue and it is the granules of eosinophils that are cytotoxic and damage the myocardium.

In the abstract of a paper that was presented at the 39th Annual Scientific Session of the American College of Cardiology, French et al (1990) in a study of 20 patients with myocarditis, 20 patients with cardiomyopathy, and 20 control patients that were age and sex matched (41 Male, 19 female, mean age 43.2), report IgE levels in the 40 patients with cardiac problems were 74.8 +/- 118 IU/ml compared with 20.9 +/- 31.2 IU/ml in the control group ($p < 0.005$). Furthermore, 8/40 test subjects had an IgE level above 100. Whilst a history of allergy, increased eosinophils or elevated IgE was found in 17/40. Finally, IgG4 levels in 7 patients with myocarditis were below the levels in all of the controls ($p < 0.05$).

Whether the decrease in IgG4 levels reported by French et al (1990) is significant to

the study that found IgG4 levels increased following a third covid vaccination as reported by Irrgang et al (2023) given that these are against the spike protein is open to question. Particularly, since IgG4 can swap FAB arms with another IgG4 (Barker 2022a) which Irrgang et al (2023) were unable to test. This raises the question as to whether the reported IgG4 subclass switch is in response not solely to the spike but also to possible allergens. Van de Veen (2016) state that IgG4 has four anti inflammatory effects, in that it is unable to form antibody complexes; has low affinity for activating Fcγ; unable to fix complement; acts as a blocking antibody to compete with IgE for allergen binding suppressing basophil and mast cell degranulation.

It might be useful to measure the amount of IgG4 and IgE in patients presenting with myocarditis associated with the CoViD-19 vaccine to determine whether there is the same correlation as determined by French et al (1990).

PEG is used as one of the nano lipids in both BNT1262b and mRNA1273 vaccines, with Polysorbate 80 being an excipient in both ChAdOx1 and Jcovden vaccines, the role of these excipients in the development of adverse effects needs to be investigated, paying particular regard to a potential role of basophils, eosinophils and mast cells. Furthermore, a specific investigation into a possible role for heparin produced in the degranulation of eosinophils and basophils, following a hypersensitivity reaction, in the development anti-PF4 antibodies as reported by Schneider et al (2021), a phenomenon noticed following heparin injections (Newman & Chong 2000).

Conclusion

Data obtained from multiple published papers on reported side effects to the four CoViD19 vaccines in use in the USA, the UK and Europe has been presented in graphical form.

Using these data the results of any diagnostic test undertaken have been examined for commonalities. These data have then been correlated to advance a hypothesis as to the possible pathogenesis of the reported side effects.

It has been recognised that further work is required to determine whether the hypothesis is valid or not, suggestions as to the nature of this additional study have been advanced.

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